

ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMMERCIAL ACTIVITIES OF TRADE ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This article examines the effectiveness of trade management, the profitability of enterprises, the implementation of commercial operations, enterprise income, the range of goods, checks their quality, high turnover, well-established economic relations and increases the pace of retail turnover, improves work with customers.*

Keywords: *commercial activity, efficiency, profitability, income, consumer, trading enterprise, service.*

Introduction. In modern conditions, enterprises are focused not only on structural and organizational development, but also on increasing the efficiency of commercial activities. In order for a trading enterprise to operate successfully, it is necessary to conduct an in-depth analysis of its commercial activities depending on the constantly changing market environment. This will make the enterprise sustainably profitable and competitive, ensure its development, and anticipate Commercial work in trade is the activity of an enterprise aimed at solving a special set of problems. Studying the processes of their implementation is an important element of operational research at the level of a trading enterprise and region.

The main participants in commercial activities are not only business structures, but also consumers. This statement is based on the fact that for entrepreneurs the most important factor when concluding transactions is income (economic benefit), and for consumers, the benefit is the product (service) they need if it satisfies their needs (consumer interests) to a greater extent. The consumer is not a passive buyer, but a full participant in commercial activity, its regulator. Thus, the most important subject of business relations between suppliers of goods and the retail chain is the consumer.

Therefore, the complex of tasks of commercial activity of subjects of the consumer market must be considered through meeting the needs of the population. The consumer, realizing his interests, has a decisive influence on the behavior of entrepreneurs in the market when concluding transactions, choosing a market segment, organizing the marketing and sale of goods, forming an assortment and pricing policy.

For an in-depth study of the impact of commercial work on the performance of enterprises, it is necessary to develop a system of the main components of its assessment, which could be used as a self-assessment of commercial work by each trading enterprise. Such a system, in our opinion, will help territorial and economic authorities determine areas for improving the management of commercial activities.

Among the tools of commercial activity of a trading enterprise, assortment policy occupies a special place. In the system for assessing commercial activities, the assortment of goods and its formation are important. The assortment renewal coefficient indicates the development and nature of economic trade relations with both domestic and foreign partners, as well as the work of enterprises to update the assortment. The assortment stability coefficient characterizes the species

composition of the goods offered in a product group (subgroup). This block is especially important for assessing the performance of enterprises selling goods from the specified assortment list.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. The assortment policy should take into account the following factors: the availability of a variety of goods in stores; stability and flexibility of the assortment, its compliance with changes in demand and seasonal fluctuations; rational placement of goods in stores.

In a market economy, the formation of an assortment is the prerogative of the trading enterprises themselves. The assortment lists in stores are based on the production and technical characteristics of the grouping of goods, which does not allow us to sufficiently take into account the complexity of demand, the complementarity of goods, seasonal features of demand development and other conditions.

The actual completeness of the assortment and its dynamics can serve as evidence of a competent assortment policy. As we have established, the completeness of the assortment depends not only on the retail space of the store and the volume of turnover. Important factors ensuring the completeness of the assortment are financial stability and the authority of the enterprise in the market of goods and services. Suppliers of goods have great confidence in stores that accept goods in large quantities, make timely payments, and have a high degree of reliability (significant turnover rates, high profitability, etc.).

To increase the social level of trade services, store sales and operational workers should pay special attention to the sustainability of the assortment. On the one hand, this indicator significantly affects the service level indicator, and on the other hand, it indicates the rhythm of deliveries. The sustainability of the assortment is a guideline for the buyer.

To characterize the efficiency of commercial activities of both an individual trading enterprise and their totality across the territory, in our opinion, the most interesting indicator is the degree of updating of the product range, that is, its replenishment with new products and products. This indicator can be defined as the renewal rate. It seems especially important for working with non-food products.

In operational work (replenishment and regulation of the assortment of a trading enterprise), we recommend using such an indicator as the share of new goods (products or products) in the volume of new arrivals, and when assessing long-term economic relations - the share of new products (products) in the total volume of goods receipts in retail network. Specialists should especially highlight products with improved consumer properties.

Calculations of the sustainability (stability) of the assortment allow us to judge the absence (presence) of interruptions in the sale of individual goods. For specialists involved in analyzing the stability of sales of goods with a fluctuating (uneven) number of purchases during the day, the introduction of such accounting will help not only evaluate the effectiveness of the organization of goods supply, but also determine the rationality of the assortment structure and the effectiveness of the assortment policy of a trading enterprise. Analysis of the breadth and sustainability (stability) of the assortment must be carried out on the basis of operational data on the state of current inventories, highlighting goods with slow turnover.

Indicators characterizing the planning of product supply and provision of goods - consists of eight indicators reflecting the planned growth of trade turnover of enterprises, changes in its

structure based on product supply, the volume of planned gross income, inventory, turnover, quality of goods. These indicators form the basis of plans for the purchase of goods, selection of suppliers, determination of delivery conditions, assortment, timing, delivery batching, prices and settlements with suppliers, etc. The higher the indices of these indicators, the more effective the economic ties. What matters here is long-termism, the degree of constancy of economic ties and, especially, the fulfillment of contractual obligations.

The effectiveness of economic relations is largely determined by the correct choice of supplier and the form of trade transactions. The number of suppliers and the frequency of delivery of goods depend on the type of store and its capacity, assortment profile, which are the determining factors in the formation of the assortment and turnover volumes. With an increase in retail space, the frequency of delivery of goods increases, and, consequently, the turnover of goods. Overall, the company's funds are spent more economically.

The greatest effectiveness of commercial activity is observed in large enterprises of various forms of ownership, which is explained by the presence of long-term economic ties with large suppliers. This ensures that specialists from this group of enterprises are highly aware of the current market situation and its prospects. Small and medium-sized enterprises, deprived of such an opportunity, most often rely in their activities on irregular, random connections.

The main suppliers of goods for them are various kinds of intermediaries, which not only complicates the actual accounting of trade turnover, but also leads to a significant increase in consumer prices and an almost complete lack of quality control of goods.

Large enterprises give preference to the quality of goods, assortment and consideration of consumer interests. Therefore, such enterprises are more preferable when the buyer chooses a place of purchase.

The formation and stimulation of demand as an area of commercial activity is inextricably linked with the blocks that characterize the planning of product supply and the formation of a product range. It is as a result of the supply of goods to the consumer that demand is formed, and as a result of the analysis of population demand, goods are purchased and the assortment and pricing policy is determined. In this process, an important place belongs to the advertising work of trading and manufacturing enterprises.

Economic efficiency of commercial activity - characterizes the effectiveness of managing the commercial work of both a specific enterprise and a set of enterprises in a certain territory. Indicators of economic efficiency of commercial activities complete and summarize the assessment of commercial activities.

In a trading enterprise, commercial activities directly affect both its economic results and the social efficiency of trade in general. The economic and social efficiency of trade are closely interrelated. The economic efficiency of commercial activities should be assessed by economic results that characterize the operation of the enterprise as a whole: general economic indicators (turnover, costs, profits, prices); indicators of resource use (production, turnover); quality of trade services (breadth, stability and renewal of the assortment); quality of goods.

The effectiveness of trade management is assessed primarily from the standpoint of the quality of trade services and the profitability of enterprises. The components of management efficiency largely depend on the organization of commercial activity and its results, since during the implementation of commercial operations trade turnover, enterprise income, assortment of goods are formed, and their quality is checked.

Analyzing the impact of commercial activities on economic results, we concluded that profitability is higher for those trading enterprises that have a wide range of goods, high turnover, well-established economic relations and are increasing the pace of retail turnover, improving their work with customers.

Assessing the commercial activities of retail enterprises, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Enterprises are gradually adapting to the market situation, and there have been positive changes in their work. Commercial trade activities have intensified to a significant extent, and there has been an improvement in the structure of trade turnover due to an increase in volume and a change in the composition of the product supply based on the expansion of the geography of interregional and international relations. The degree of satisfaction of consumer demand has increased, both in volume and structure. This is due to the expansion, updating of the range and promotion to the market of fundamentally new areas of goods and services for the population.

Due to the development and deepening of the scope of activity of economic entities, the substantive aspect of the commercial activities of trading enterprises has fundamentally changed. Nowadays, a significant part of retail enterprises combine wholesale and retail sales, and wholesale enterprises combine wholesale and retail sales. They are expanding retail trade and manufacturing enterprises, thereby ensuring the maneuverability of commodity resources, the rapid delivery of goods to consumers and the return on investment.

Our research did not reveal significant changes in the organization of commercial activities at enterprises, in the work of the services involved in it, in the content and rational distribution of responsibilities between employees in the approach to solving problems. As before, the main commercial functions are carried out by business managers, which is especially true for local shops and limited liability companies. Due to workload and lack of knowledge of market processes and little experience of working in new conditions, these specialists do not ensure high efficiency of commercial activities in all areas.

The expansion of the trading network and the emergence of new types of trading enterprises have ensured an influx of workers into trade who do not have special training and do not have the necessary set of knowledge, as evidenced by data from official statistics, sample surveys and expert surveys. At the same time, the professional level and established stereotypes of the activities of personnel workers of certain categories often conflict with the requirements of the changed conditions of the external and internal environment of the enterprise.

An analysis of the effectiveness of commercial activities of trading enterprises showed its greatest effectiveness in large enterprises. But small stores are closest to the consumer. Their activities require full support from the state. In particular, it is necessary to establish information market centers in places that would provide various enterprises with the necessary information about market conditions, market processes, etc. This can play a positive role both in terms of increasing the efficiency of trading activities and in terms of creating a favorable market environment.

The lack of market information, operational analysis data and the inability to constantly link commercial decisions with market conditions reduce the efficiency of trade specialists. This is especially clearly manifested in the weakened attention to the work of studying the demand for goods directly at the trading enterprise. Here the work on generating consumer demand with the help of the necessary information and advertising is weakened.

It is necessary to introduce marketing services (or at least their basic elements) at every trading enterprise. Since marketing is a purely market concept for managing the commercial activities of an enterprise, it allows the most harmonious combination of the market interests of the enterprise and the consumer. Practical marketing will bring real benefits to an enterprise only if its application is carried out by qualified specialists with knowledge in the field of market strategy and tactics.

The development of marketing services is hampered by the lack of funds from enterprises, specially trained personnel and methodological developments adapted to local conditions.

Effective commercial activity at the regional level ensures market saturation, a high level of consumer satisfaction, and the development of competition in the sphere of circulation and therefore should be an area of constant attention of government authorities. Control over individual areas of commercial activity (prices, trade markups, taxes), carried out today by disparate, narrow departmental structures, does not allow obtaining a holistic picture of the ongoing processes, much less ensuring comprehensive management of them.

It is known that the resources of an enterprise and the requirements of profitable operation to a certain extent limit maneuvering both in the range of goods and in their prices. But it is the focus on customer demand and its active formation that should determine the use of available resources. The successful sale of goods ensures the efficiency of the enterprise.

Assessing the efficiency of commercial activities of enterprises is necessary when planning economic activities, identifying the reasons for failure to meet planned targets, finding reserves for increasing the efficiency of the enterprise, and determining its development strategy. An assessment of commercial activity gives an idea of the enterprise's adaptation to market conditions, allows not only to develop a strategy and tactics for the behavior of trading enterprises, but also to increase the efficiency of their management at the territory level. Its application allows business entities to determine the strengths and weaknesses of trading activities and concentrate all conditions on the areas that are the most promising and profitable.

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